

Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen
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MrDataSearch - Medical Research Metadata Search using an RDF Graph Database

Cato Elia Kurtz

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Reviewer

Prof. Dr. Thomas Walter
Department of Computer Science
University of Tübingen

Supervisors

Dr. Heinrich Lautenbacher
Faculty of Medicine
University of Tübingen

Blake G. Fitch
Max Planck Institute for Biological Cybernetics

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Abstract

Good data management is a cornerstone of research that helps with knowledge discovery and innovation. In this thesis I describe the MrDataSearch tool I developed to increase searchability for medical research metadata in the MrData Project at the Max Planck Institute for Biological Cybernetics. This work was done using the Python programming language to extract metadata from the MrData archival system and organizing it in a graph database which can then be queried with the SPARQL query language. Early feedback from end-users is promising, and the implementation can already answer most of the researchers' metadata searches, filling in earlier gaps in searchability. Future work in collaboration with the Max Planck Institute for Biological Cybernetics will expand and improve this project, in particular enhancing end-user access via a graphical user interface.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

“Good data management is not a goal in itself, but rather is the key conduit leading to knowledge discovery and innovation, and to subsequent data and knowledge integration and reuse by the community after the data publication process.”[1]

That is the first sentence of the 2016 paper “The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship”. It highlights the importance of good data management in research. This is the motivation for the work in this thesis on the MrDataSearch tool.

For this work, I cooperated with the Max Planck Institute (MPI) for Biological Cybernetics to increase searchability of metadata for their magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) research data. The MPI for Biological Cybernetics has an internally developed archival system called MrData[2], which automates collection, metadata extraction, and archival of MRI data. MrData utilizes the Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System (iRODS) as the storage engine for MRI medical research data, which includes metadata management features used by the MrData system. But challenges remained for several types of metadata searches.

To help the researchers by improving the quality of data management, thereby making their research data more accessible and reusable, a graph database was designed to address a set of example queries provided by neuroscientists. This graph database is created and updated through a Python script that scans the iRODS archive for metadata and creates Resource Description Framework (RDF) triples with the retrieved information. The goal was to put the existing metadata in a format which makes it easier for researchers to filter their experiments and studies according to specific metadata criteria. This could benefit not only the researchers at the MPI for Biological Cybernetics, but also be used at other institutes in the future.

1.1 Background

At the MPI for Biological Cybernetics, Fitch et al. developed the MrData System[2], an iRODS based archival system, which is used for medical image data produced by human subject research. MrData is currently used to automatically collect and archive the data from Siemens 9.4 Tesla and Siemens 3 Tesla MRI systems scanning human subjects. It archives MRI image data using two systems: Castellum[3], an open source system designed by the MPI for human development to manage human subjects' person identifiable information (PII) securely, and iRODS [4], a widely used open source data management software.

MrData[2] differentiates between subject recruiting metadata and scientific metadata. Subject recruiting data are highly sensitive PII while scientific metadata are considered anonymized but necessary for long term retention and reuse in support of FAIR principles for good data management. Mixed use metadata i.e. data needed for both the recruiting and scientific interpretation, is another category of metadata. This can include information such as a subject's age, handedness or gender.

Figure 1.1: Mixed use metadata. Modified from:[2]

In MrData, Castellum is employed as a subject management system which takes care of all recruiting metadata in a General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliant way. Only mixed use metadata, explicitly authorized for export, then get exported to iRODS with a one-way Castellum API specifically designed for MrData. This ensures that all data stored in MrData can be considered anonymized in this context and free of PII.

Figure 1.2: Mixed use metadata move one-way from Castellum to MrData. Modified from:[2]

The goal of this thesis is to increase searchability by metadata for scientific researchers. Therefore, the rest of this thesis will focus on enabling the search of scientific and mixed-use data and metadata recorded by MrData in iRODS.

1.2 Problem and Motivation

A problem with MrData was that researchers at the MPI for Biological Cybernetics faced difficulties filtering their research data by metadata using the search tools available in iRODS.

Specific aspects they struggled with were:

- listing all experiments for a specific subject whose scientific metadata fulfilled certain criteria (e.g. db_MPRAGE¹ with voxelSz² = [8.0,8.0,8.0] and FOV³ > [180,160,120])
- determining if two experiments belonged to the same subject
- selecting all subjects with certain metadata criteria like left-handedness and returning functional data on them
- runtime: queries they posed to iRODS sometimes took over one minute to run, which the researchers considered too slow.

To further investigate these problems, I looked into different existing iRODS tools for metadata search to figure out if they could already satisfy the researchers' specific needs.

In their FAQ, iRODS highlighted two iCommands which could be used to search iRODS metadata: imeta and iquest. Both can be used to query for

¹A version of the common Magnetization-Prepared Rapid Gradient Echo (MP RAGE) MRI Sequence [5] implemented here by Dario Bosch

²"Voxel Size", size of the volume pixels in the MRI scan

³"Field of View", the volume of the MRI picture taken

specific values in the attribute value units (AVUs), the format that iRODS uses to store its metadata. The problem: in the case of MrData the metadata relevant for filtering were not only stored as attributes with values in the specific iRODS metadata AVUs, but could also be found in the file system structure. For instance, if experiment folders were saved inside a study folder, this indicated that those experiments belonged to that particular study. This kind of information was often not saved as specific iRODS metadata on all files or folders it applied to. To further illustrate this, a sketch of the MrData iRODS file system structure can be found in 1.3

Figure 1.3: Sketch of the MrData iRODS file system structure

Another issue was that different metadata were saved for different files or folders and not redundantly for everything it applied to. Mixed use metadata about a subject could therefore be saved in one place, scanner settings that were used for an experiment saved in another place, and which subjects took part in which experiments would be saved in a third, completely different place.

The options and examples in the iRODS documentation on `imeta` and `iquest` suggest, there is no way to create an iRODS metadata search that pulls knowledge from more than one metadata path in the file tree. There also is no option to use folder or file names in paths for iRODS metadata search. It is limited to AVU triples saved in one location, i.e. on one file or folder.

Based on these limitations in the query infrastructure, I investigated developing an alternative solution that did not rely on iRODS' `iquest` or `imeta`. To address these issues, this thesis explores the use of a graph database structure for storing the research data and to connect the metadata in a way that increases searchability. This solution is called `MrDataSearch`.

1.3 Structure of the thesis

This thesis is structured as follows: The basics of the problem and relevant background information are given in chapter 1. Chapter 2 introduces the tools used for this project and how the task was approached. After that, we look into the details of the Implementation in chapter 3. The Results and Discussion can then be found in chapter 4 and after that, a brief outlook in chapter 5 concludes the work.

Chapter 2

Materials and Methods

2.1 Tools

2.1.1 iRODS

iRODS, the Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System, is the tool currently used to save MRI experiment data and metadata as part of the MrData system. It is an open source data management software widely used in different fields worldwide [4].

In an iRODS system, most of the data are saved in a file system, with folders called “collections” and files called “data objects” [6]. Some of those collections and data objects then also have metadata on them, which iRODS saves as AVU triples in an internally managed relational database.

2.1.2 Database Management Systems

A database management system (DBMS) is a system used to control a database, which can be any organized collection of structured data [7]. Together, the DBMS and the data are called a database system or just a database.

There are many different types of DBMSs, the most common one being the relational database management system (RDBMS) [8]. The top 4 most popular DBMSs were relational and out of the top 10, 7 were relational DBMSs in August 2024 according to the DB-Engines Ranking. In the following we will explore relational and graph databases, as those are the two relevant types for this project.

Relational Database

The relational database management system (RDBMS) is the most widely used type of DBMS [8]. According to the iRODS documentation it is also the type of DBMS that iRODS uses to store and access its metadata information [6].

An RDBMS organizes its data in rows and columns of tables [9]. Different related data points are usually spread across different tables and can be identified with keys.

RDF Graph Database

The Resource Description Framework (RDF) is a framework recommended by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) for representing information on the web [10]. It contains an RDF graph, a data structure used as the graph database model in MrDataSearch.

Unlike a relational database, an RDF graph saves its information in triples consisting of a subject, a predicate and an object. Triples can be visualized as a node-arc-node link, which also means that each RDF graph can be visualized as a node and directed-arc diagram.

Figure 2.1: Visualization of an RDF Triple [11]

The textual syntax for RDF used in this project is the Terse RDF Triple Language (Turtle) [12]. A Turtle file contains an RDF graph in a compact and natural text form.

To query the RDF graph database, the W3C recommended SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language (SPARQL) was used [13].

2.1.3 Python libraries

Most of the code for MrDataSearch was written in Python 3.10.12 [14]. The three main libraries that were used are introduced below.

mrdata common public

Mrdata common public is a gitlab repository at the MPI for Biological Cybernetics that contains shred components of the MrData system [15]. It contains utility functions for the MrData system used by multiple components,

including the function `get_irods_session_from_cred_yaml`, which was used in `MrDataSearch` to connect to the `MrData` iRODS storage.

Python iRODS Client (PRC)

The Python iRODS Client is a Python library for iRODS used in `mrdata` common public and directly in the code for `MrDataSearch`. It provides all the tools for the programmatic interactions with iRODS and is used e.g. in creating an iRODS session or accessing the iRODS metadata of a collection or data object.

RDFLib

RDFLib is a Python library for working with RDF [16]. In `MrDataSearch`, it was used to build the metadata graph database using Python and then export it into a Turtle file.

2.1.4 Apache Jena Fuseki

Apache Jena Fuseki is a SPARQL server that can be run locally. To test `MrDataSearch`, an Ubuntu-based version of this server by Ryan Baumann [17] was used. It provides a graphical web interface, which users can run locally. RDF datasets in the form of Turtle files can be loaded into Fuseki and then queried via SPARQL.

2.2 Approach

When starting to work on this project, I first familiarized myself with `MrData`, iRODS and graph databases. Then I assessed the currently available options for metadata search in iRODS, described in 1.2, evaluating them based on an example set of queries provided by the neuroscientists. This assessment led to the conclusion that developing a new solution would be best for solving these issues.

Since Python tools for `MrData` already existed in the library `mrdata_common_public` [15], and were used by `MrData` to create the data and metadata archive, we decided that it would be best for me to also develop `MrDataSearch` in Python.

The first step of development was to get access to the `MrData` iRODS archive using Python. Then, by extracting the archive structure and metadata information from iRODS, a graph database was built by a Python script. The initial approach was to be as generic as possible, which resulted in a graph database similar to the sketch in Figure 1.3 that included the iRODS

file system structure as RDF triples, used paths as unique identifiers and had some metadata connections on top that were supposed to increase searchability.

The graph database created by this initial approach was then loaded into Apache Jena Fuseki and the neuroscientists were invited to test it. Based on the feedback from this initial prototype, a second graph database was designed which focused more on directly relevant triple connections for MRI researchers. The second version was first designed as a sketch of the graph database with concepts and instances of those concepts, after researching ontology graphs. The sketch was then updated through several rounds of feedback. After that, a graph database generator, implementing the new design, was developed in Python. This second implementation, the results that came from testing it with queries and feedback from researchers, will be subject to chapters 3 and 4.

Chapter 3

Implementation

3.1 RDF Graph Design

Before implementing this current version of the MrDataSearch graph database covered in this thesis, I first sketched out my design ideas and discussed them in depth with people from the MrData Team. Once I was satisfied the design would meet the requirements, I started the python implementation.

Figure 3.1 now shows the design sketch, which visualizes the structure of the graph database. The ovals demonstrate important concepts in this context, like a study or an experiment, that will get a formal ontology definition in the future. The larger square fields demonstrate instances of concepts. They are collections or data objects in iRODS and therefore also all have a path in iRODS that can be returned by MrDataSearch. The smaller square boxes, which all contain the word “literal”, demonstrate literal metadata values that belong to an instance of a concept.

The three main concepts are the study, the experiment and the subject. The goal of this graph design was to translate the existing relationships of those concepts and all attached data into connections in a graph database. The instances of those three concepts have metadata on them. Therefore, those connections were added as triples where the instance is the subject, the metadata attribute is the predicate, and the value is the object.

A study can have multiple experiments, an experiment has one subject and a subject can take part in any number of experiments. While the IDs for studies and experiments are unique throughout the MrData system, subject IDs are only unique within one study. This is because Castellum assigns the same person taking part in multiple studies a new subject ID in each one. As the subject IDs are generated randomly within a set scheme, it is also not guaranteed that the same subject ID will not be given out twice in different studies.

Figure 3.1: RDF Graph design for MrDataSearch

This means that on one hand we cannot search for information about a subject across multiple studies as the link between subject IDs and each individual is stored in Castellum only. Since MrDataSearch only works with data extracted from iRODS, this information was not available while building the MrDataSearch graph. On the other hand, if we want to prevent accidentally mixing up information on different subjects due to identical IDs in different studies, we must add something to the subject IDs to make them unique across studies. To address that and create a unique subject ID in the metadata graph, the corresponding study ID was prepended to each subject ID, since subject IDs are unique within each study.

The relationships between instances of studies, experiments and subjects are described by RDF triples in the graph database, where the instances are subjects and objects. Specific predicates that start with “has” or “belongsTo”, depending on the relationship they describe, connect them.

In the lower half of 3.1, we can see four connections that start from the instance of an experiment and all begin with “has”. Those relationships connect experiment data, which come in the form of Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) [18] series, Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative (NIfTI) [19] series, raw image data and additional experiment data to their corresponding experiment.

A DICOM series is a series of MRI images in the DICOM file format directly created on the local MRI system using the vendor-provided software. For convenience these DICOM series get translated into the NIfTI standard directly within the pipeline of MrData using the open source tool dcm2niix [20]. This is due to the fact that the majority of users will request the NIfTI format. In this particular case, a DICOM series produces up to three NIfTI series because in the conversion process from DICOM to NIfTI the three anatomical planes stored in one DICOM file get split up into one NIfTI file each. Therefore the concept node for these three NIfTI series for one DICOM series is currently “partialDicomSeries”.

The raw image data are raw Siemens image data in a proprietary format called TWIX [21]. It is saved in MrData because some local research involves investigation into the conversion of raw data to image data. Additional experiment data are all the other data the scientists might wish to archive in association with an experiment, but is not one of the three kinds of image data described above. For example for functional MRI experiments, this might include audio files containing the stimulus subjects experience during the MRI session.

Concept nodes in the graph design were created for all four types of experiment data, to make the instances searchable by concept type.

The three image data types (DICOM series, NIfTI series and TWIX raw data) all have the same metadata for a given scan sequence because they all contain the same medical image data in different formats. These metadata were added to the graph in the same way as the metadata for instances of studies, experiments and subjects.

3.2 Python Implementation

3.2.1 Creation of the graph and the nodes for concepts and predicates

Before an RDF graph can be built and filled with information gathered from iRODS, it needs to be initialized as a data structure in Python. Global variables for later use in the graph building process are also initialized.

```

g = Graph()

#Nodes for concepts
study = URIRef("study")
experiment = URIRef("experiment")
subject = URIRef("subject")
rawData = URIRef("rawData")
dicomSeries = URIRef("dicomSeries")
partialDicomSeries = URIRef("partialDicomSeries")
expData = URIRef("expData")

#Nodes for predicates (relationships)
#all files in the graph have a path
hasPath = URIRef("hasPath")
#study has experiment
hasExp = URIRef("hasExperiment")
#study/experiment has subject
hasSubj = URIRef("hasSubject")
#subject belongs to exp
belongsToExp = URIRef("belongsToExp")
#subject/exp belongs to study
belongsToStudy = URIRef("belongsToStudy")
#an experiment can have Dicom Series'
hasDicomSeries = URIRef("hasDicomSeries")
#the series can have NIFTI files
hasNiftiFile = URIRef("hasNiftiFile")
#an experiment can have ExpData
hasExpData = URIRef("hasExpData")
#an experiment can have raw data files
hasRawDataFile = URIRef("hasRawDataFile")

```

Figure 3.2: Code for setting up the graph, concept and predicate nodes

The graph itself as well as the concept and predicate nodes that get used to connect instances of concepts are initialized globally and outline the RDF triple predicates that will be used. This allows the reader to get a quick overview of their name and use. It also makes it easy to add, remove or change concepts, predicates, or just their names, because they are all defined in one place and are not spread across the different functions.

3.2.2 Extraction of Data from iRODS

In order to access the data to build the graph database from iRODS, the python script makes a connection to iRODS from Python via the function `get_irods_session_from_cred_yaml` from the library `mrdata` common public [15] in the function `get_irods_session`. That way, `get_irods_session` can be called in the main graph building function to build an iRODS session, and all details on building the session stay in that function.

```
import irods_utils as iutils

cred_file_path = "irods_search_credential_file.yml"
cafile = "cacert.pem"

#sets up a mrdata session and base ipath with given cred and ca file.
#uses the files specified above, if none are given.
def get_irods_session(cred_file_path = cred_file_path, cafile = cafile):
    try:
        mrdata_irods_sesh, mrdata_base_ipath =
            iutils.get_irods_session_from_cred_yaml(cred_file_path, cafile)
        print(f"irods_user: {mrdata_irods_sesh.username}")
        print(f"irods_zone: {mrdata_irods_sesh.zone}")
        print(f"irods_user_path: {mrdata_base_ipath}")

    except:
        raise Exception("FATAL: Failed to get an iRODS session")

    return mrdata_irods_sesh, mrdata_base_ipath

#takes directory where the crawl to build the graph should start
#walks through the file system and builds a graph DB with rdf triples
#along the way
def build_graph(dir = "/MRDataZone/home"):
    irods_sesh, irods_ipath = get_irods_session()

    #generator object with all data objects and subcollections in given dir
    walker = irods_sesh.collections.get(dir).walk()

    #extract the names of all collections/data objects
    for coll in walker: #one parent collection with everything it contains
        parent_coll, child_colls, data_objects = coll
```

Figure 3.3: Relevant code excerpts for getting the MrData iRODS data into Python

The paths to the credential file and the certificate, which are used to build the iRODS connection, were added as global variables at the beginning of the file, so they could easily be found and changed. For the `get_irods_session` function, both of these were added as default input. As a result, the function does not need to be called with parameters, but can be called with specific ones if different credentials or a different certificate are needed.

In the `get_irods_session` function, “try...except” was used to build an iRODS session with the given credentials, return the session, print some information about it if that is possible, and return an error otherwise.

Continuing with the main function `build_graph`, we can see that the first step to build a graph, is to call the function `get_irods_session` mentioned above to build a connection to the MrData iRODS storage, from which we then extract the data to build the graph.

The newly created iRODS session then gets used with the `walk` function from the Python iRODS Client [22] to go over the whole MrData archive in iRODS, creating a generator object called `walker`. On demand, the `walker` can then “walk” over all subcollections and data objects of the collection pointed to by the path that was given to the `build_graph` function as `dir`.

This is also what happens in the next loop: The `walker` is used to access one (sub-) collection at a time, extract the (parent-) collection itself, its sub-/child- collections and contained data objects. These then all get used in different ways in the following code to build the RDF graph.

3.2.3 Building the RDF Graph (`build_graph`)

The main function of the Python script that builds the graph database is called `build_graph`. It creates an instance of a generator object called `walker`. The `walker` is used to “walk” over all (sub-)collections of a specified path in iRODS and builds the graph along that “walk”.

For every collection the `walker` “walks” through, the code checks if the collection name matches a set of keywords. If it matches and either contains studies, an experiment, subjects, or one of the four types of experiment data, that collection contains data needed for the graph, an RDF triple is formed and a function gets called to add it to the graph.

Every time a path or name from iRODS gets added to an RDF triple, the code uses the function `quote` from the Python library `urllib.parse`[23], to make sure the resulting URIs only contain valid characters, so they can then be serialized into a Turtle file.

If the name of the current iRODS parent collection is “studies” or “subjects”, that collection contains studies or subjects as subcollections respectively. The code then iterates over all child collections and adds them as nodes to the graph with the function `add_node`. In the case of subjects, we also need to add the study ID to each subject node because the subject IDs on their own are not unique identifiers. Since the folder “subjects” only appears in one place in the MrData file system structure, we can rely on that file system structure of the path leading up to the subject’s folder. The code extracts the study ID from the path and then uses it to add it to the URI of the subject node.

Not all experiments have a parent collection called “experiments”, like the parent folders for studies and subjects. The code therefore relies on the specific pattern of experiment IDs. That pattern always consists of two sets of four characters separated by a dash and gets matched with a regex expression against the current parent collection name. If it matches, that (parent-) collection is an experiment. The following code then handles that (parent-) collection the same way as the child collections of the “studies” and “experiments” parent folders.

If a collection matches the experiment pattern, we also need to check if we are currently in the iRODS directory “mrdataforms”. In this case, we also give that experiment collection to the function `make_ses_connections` because experiment collections in mrdataforms also contain the information which study, experiment and subject belong together as metadata.

If the name of a (parent-) collection matches one of the names of collections that contain a type of experiment data, that collection gets passed on to `add_data_objects`. That function also takes the experiment ID of the collection (which we extract with `get_exp_id`), the data objects contained as well as the matching predicate and concept to be placed in the graph. It then uses this information to add the data objects in that collection, which contain experiment data, to the graph.

Once the `walker` is done with its “walk” over all collections for a given path, all relevant data have been added to the graph and the finished graph can be serialized into a Turtle file. Once that serialization process is done without errors, we print out “yay” to the command line to symbolize that everything in the graph building process succeeded.

```

#takes directory where the crawl to build the graph should start
#walks through the file system and builds a graph DB with rdf triples along the
way
def build_graph(dir = "/MRDataZone/home"):
    irods_sesh, irods_ipath = get_irods_session()

    #generator object with all data objects and subcollections in given dir
    walker = irods_sesh.collections.get(dir).walk()

    #extract the names of all collections/data objects
    for coll in walker: #one parent collection with everything it contains (
        subcollections/data objects)

        parent_coll, child_colls, data_objects = coll

        #make sure to only have uri valid chars in paths/names
        parent_path = quote(parent_coll.path)

        #add nodes with path to graph and connect them with their path
        if (parent_coll.name == "studies"):
            for child_coll in child_colls:
                study_node = URIRef(quote(child_coll.name))
                add_node(study_node, study, child_coll)

        elif re.match(r"....-...." , parent_coll.name):
            exp_node = URIRef(quote(parent_coll.name))
            add_node(exp_node, experiment, parent_coll)
            #if we are in mrdataforms
            if re.match(r"*/././....-...." , parent_path):
                make_ses_connections(parent_coll)

        elif (parent_coll.name == "subjects"):
            #get study id from path (subjects folder only exists in castellum
            folder)

            pattern = r'/(\\d+)/' + parent_coll.name
            match = re.search(pattern, parent_coll.path)
            study_id = match.group(1)
            for child_coll in child_colls:
                #subjectid is only unique within one study, [studyid,
                subjectid] is unique
                #one person has different subject ids in different studies
                subj_node = URIRef(study_id + "_" + quote(child_coll.name))
                add_node(subj_node, subject, child_coll)

        #partial dicom series (one dicom gets split into up to 3 nifti files,
        #one for every layer)
        elif (parent_coll.name == "DICOM_NIFTI"):
            add_data_objects(URIRef(get_exp_id(parent_coll)), data_objects,
                hasNiftiFile,
                partialDicomSeries)

        #dicom series (each tgz file is one series)
        elif (parent_coll.name == "DICOM_TGZ"):
            add_data_objects(URIRef(get_exp_id(parent_coll)), data_objects,
                hasDicomSeries, dicomSeries
            )

        #all additional experiment data
        elif (parent_coll.name == "EXPDATA"):
            add_data_objects(URIRef(get_exp_id(parent_coll)), data_objects,
                hasExpData, expData)

        #siemens raw data files
        elif (parent_coll.name == "TWIX"):
            add_data_objects(URIRef(get_exp_id(parent_coll)), data_objects,
                hasRawDataFile, rawData)

    #store finished graph
    g.serialize(destination="graph2.ttl")
    print("yay!")

```

Figure 3.4: Code for the main function `build_graph` which builds the Mr-DataSearch RDF graph with data from the MrData iRODS storage

3.2.4 Adding data objects to the graph (add_data_objects)

This function adds RDF triples to the graph database for a given set of (experiment) data objects. For each data object, it creates a node and adds three RDF triples containing that node to the graph. One triple is to connect the data object as subject with a given node as object, using a given predicate. For instance, if our set of data objects are DICOM series in a specific experiment, this triple would connect each data object node with the node of the experiment via the given predicate “hasDicomSeries”. The second triple is to connect each new data object node to the path the data object had in iRODS in order to make that data object findable in iRODS. The third triple is to connect the data object to its concept node (e.g. dicomSeries) via the built-in predicate `RDF.type`.

If a data object contains metadata, the code uses the function `add_metadata` to also add that metadata to the graph. Because some metadata threw errors in development, there was also a “try...except” added to catch metadata that triggers an error and print out where that triggering metadata are stored in iRODS.

```
#takes a node, a list of data objects, a predicate, and a type for the data
                                objects
#adds them as (node, predicate, data object) triples to the graph
#then also adds path and type to the object nodes
def add_data_objects(node, data_objects, predicate, obj_type):
    for obj in data_objects:
        #make sure to only have uri valid chars in paths/names
        path = quote(obj.path)
        obj_node = URIRef(quote(obj.name))
        g.add((node, predicate, obj_node))
        g.add((obj_node, hasPath, Literal(path)))
        g.add((obj_node, RDF.type, obj_type))

        #check for metadata
        try:
            if obj.metadata.items() != []:
                add_metadata(obj, obj_node)
        except Exception as error:
            print(f"metadata on here: {path}\nthrows error:\n{error}")
```

Figure 3.5: Code for the `add_data_objects` function

3.2.5 Adding relationships between studies, experiments and subjects (make_ses_connections)

Experiments are registered in the MrData System by a web service called MrData Forms [2]. When a user registers an experiment in MrData Forms, they have to fill in their user id, a subject pseudonym the subject ID and the study ID, to which MrData Forms then associates an experiment ID that gets used in place of a subject name at the scanner. This allows MrData to archive data by experiments and keeps all PII in one place.

For MrDataSearch this means that the only place where we can get the information on which study, experiment and subject ID belong together, which we need to build our RDF graph, is MrData Forms. In iRODS, “mrdataforms” is a collection, and only the metadata on one certain subcollection of it store that information for each experiment.

`make_ses_connections` uses those metadata from a specific collection in `mrdataforms` to form the connections between the studies, experiments and subjects in our graph database: The code first creates variables for the three IDs. It then iterates over the metadata for the given collection and fills in the three newly created variables with the actual IDs saved in the metadata. After that, the code then creates triples for all six connections between a study, an experiment and a subject. Because the subject ID on its own is not unique, this function uses a combination of the subject ID and its study ID in the triples to have a unique identifier for a subject.

```
#takes a collection in mrdataforms that has metadata about study/exp/subj
#who belong together and make connections in graph between them
def make_ses_connections(coll):
    study_id = ""
    exp_id = ""
    subj_id = ""
    for item in coll.metadata.items():
        if item.name == "StudyId":
            study_id = item.value
        if item.name == "ExperimentId":
            exp_id = item.value
        if item.name == "SubjectId":
            subj_id = item.value
    g.add((URIRef(study_id), hasExp, URIRef(exp_id)))
    g.add((URIRef(study_id), hasSubj, URIRef(study_id + "_" + subj_id)))
    g.add((URIRef(exp_id), belongsToStudy, URIRef(study_id)))
    g.add((URIRef(exp_id), hasSubj, URIRef(study_id + "_" + subj_id)))
    g.add((URIRef(study_id + "_" + subj_id), belongsToExp, URIRef(exp_id)))
    g.add((URIRef(study_id + "_" + subj_id), belongsToStudy, URIRef(study_id)))
    )
```

Figure 3.6: Code for the `make_ses_connections` function

3.2.6 Extracting the experiment ID from a path (get_exp_id)

When adding experiment data objects (e.g. DICOM series), we extract the ID of the experiment they belong to from the iRODS path. Since the collections for these experiment data are subcollections of collections with the experiment ID of the experiment they belong to as names, this can easily be done with a small function. `get_exp_id` takes a collection and then uses regex pattern matching to extract the experiment ID from its path and return it.

```
#takes an experiment collection
#and extracts the experiment id from the path
def get_exp_id(coll):
    pattern = r'/(...-...)/' + coll.name
    match = re.search(pattern, coll.path)
    return match.group(1)
```

Figure 3.7: Code for the `get_exp_id` function

3.2.7 Adding a node to the graph (add_node)

This function is used to add the nodes for all studies, experiments and subjects to the RDF graph. `add_node` is a function that takes a node, a concept node and an iRODS collection and adds their combinations to the graph as follows: At first, it extracts the path from the given collection. After that, two triples get added to the graph: one that connects the node (e.g. “42”) with the concept node (e.g. “study”) as its type and one that connects the node with the path that has been extracted in the first step.

```
#takes a node, together with the concept node and irods collection that
#belongs to it and adds node to graph with type, path & metadata
def add_node(node, concept_node, coll):
    path = quote(coll.path)
    g.add((node, RDF.type, concept_node))
    g.add((node, hasPath, Literal(path)))
    #add metadata if it exists
    try:
        if coll.metadata.items() != []:
            add_metadata(coll, node)
    except Exception as error:
        print(f"metadata on here: {path}\nthrows error:\n{error}")
```

Figure 3.8: Code for the `add_node` function

At the end of the function, we then also add possible metadata in a “try...except” like in `add_data_objects` to catch metadata that triggers errors. If there is metadata on the given collection that doesn’t trigger an error we use `add_metadata` to also add it to our node.

3.2.8 Adding metadata to nodes in the graph (`add_metadata`)

`add_metadata` gets called in multiple other functions and is responsible for adding metadata on a given iRODS collection or data object to the given node in the graph. The code achieves this using a for loop to go over all metadata on the given iRODS collection or data object and then adding them.

Because metadata in iRODS are always saved as attribute value units (AVUs) and `MrData` only uses the attribute and value fields, we can use those as predicate and object in our RDF triples. We extract both of them, use “quote” to make sure they only contain valid URI characters and then add them to the graph in a triple with the given node they belong to as the subject.

```
#takes collumn or object and its node
#and adds metadata from coll/obj onto the node in the graph
def add_metadata(coll_obj, node):
    for item in coll_obj.metadata.items():
        #make sure to only have uri valid chars in paths/names
        name = quote(item.name)
        value = quote(item.value)
        g.add((node, URIRef(name), Literal(value)))
```

Figure 3.9: Code for the `add_metadata` function

Chapter 4

Results and Discussion

4.1 Testing

Since Turtle is a human-readable format for RDF graphs [12], the generated graph database was manually inspected to see that it conformed to the design shown in figure 3.1. After several iterations of checking the output Turtle file to see if the connections there matched the ones sketched out for the graph, and then going back to fix the code, the script produced a Turtle file with connections that matched the graph design.

The Turtle file was then uploaded to a local Apache Jena Fuseki Server for testing with SPARQL queries such as the following:

- Return all experiment IDs for experiments (within one study) that used the same subject as experiment EJZX-PAYC
- Return all experiment IDs for experiments in study 41 that contain a DICOM Series, whose protocol name contains the word “MPRAGE”
- Return all experiment IDs and filenames of raw data files in study 41, where that raw data file belongs to the experiment and contains the words “MPRAGE” and “Husten” in its protocol name.
- Return all experiment IDs and filenames of raw data files, where that raw data file belongs to the experiment and contains the letter “A” in its protocol name.
- Return all experiment IDs of experiments in study 41, where both “Husten” and “Raeuspern” were tested

At first, some queries were designed and tested by me to check some basic expected outputs and test if we could now design queries to address the previous struggles with metadata searchability described by neuroscientists. In the

next step I invited them to pose some more example queries to further test the system. After all those queries produced the expected outputs in testing and took no more than a few seconds to run, the implementation was considered successful.

The screenshot shows the Apache Jena Fuseki web interface in a browser window. The browser tab is titled "Apache Jena Fuseki - insp x" and the address bar shows "localhost:3030/dataset.html?tab=query&ds=/MrDataSea". The interface includes a navigation bar with "dataset", "manage datasets", and "help" links, and a "Server status" indicator.

The main content area is titled "Dataset: /MrDataSearch_graph2" and contains a "query" section. The "SPARQL query" section includes a text area with the following query:

```

1 SELECT ?experiment
2 WHERE
3 {
4   <http://localhost:3030/41> <http://localhost:3030/hasExperiment> ?experiment .
5   ?experiment <http://localhost:3030/hasRawDataFile> ?raw_data_file_1 .
6   ?experiment <http://localhost:3030/hasRawDataFile> ?raw_data_file_2 .
7   FILTER regex(STR(?m), "Raeuspern", "i") .
8   ?raw_data_file_1 <http://localhost:3030/ProtocolName> ?m
9   FILTER regex(STR(?n), "Husten", "i") .
10  ?raw_data_file_2 <http://localhost:3030/ProtocolName> ?n
11 }

```

Below the query is the "QUERY RESULTS" section, which shows a table with one entry:

experiment
1 <http://localhost:3030/GGBK-FOWO>

The interface also includes options for "upload files", "edit", "info", "EXAMPLE QUERIES", "PREFIXES", "SPARQL ENDPOINT", "CONTENT TYPE (SELECT)", and "CONTENT TYPE (GRAPH)".

Figure 4.1: Screenshot of querying with Apache Jena Fuseki

4.2 Feedback

Since MrDataSearch can answer queries that were not able to be answered before with the metadata search tools in iRODS, the feedback from the MrData team was positive. What they liked about MrDataSearch, was the fact that they could now filter their MRI data via metadata criteria stored in different locations. Other points they were pleased about were the shorter runtime of mostly under one second for queries and the fact that new data could be added to the graph without much effort. Since the Python script building the graph lets users specify the path from which it takes its source, one can select the directory with new data that needs to be added to the graph and then append the output from running the script to the existing Turtle file to add that new information to the graph.

The neuroscience researchers also had some feedback on features they wanted to be added or improved in the future. One request was the option to filter for the same subject across multiple studies. In order to filter for that information MrDataSearch would need access to data in Castellum. Subject IDs are only unique within one study, the same person has different subject IDs in different studies and only Castellum provides access to all of them.

In that context we also talked about the possibility to restrict user access to certain data, meaning that some data (like a unique identifier for a person) could be used in MrDataSearch to filter data, but not be given out to the user. In the current human-readable Turtle format for the graph database this is not possible yet.

Another issue discussed was accessibility for scientific end-users. The current option of writing SPARQL queries to the graph Database is not very accessible for researchers, since none of the MrData researchers currently know how to write SPARQL queries.

We are considering a range of possible solutions for these issues, that we want to explore in the future as discussed in section 5.2.

4.3 Implementation Challenges

During the implementation phase I overcame several challenges that might be of interest to people who want to work with MrDataSearch or intend to create something similar. These struggles will now be discussed in this section.

One issue I struggled with is understanding how and where which metadata was stored in MrData. Not all metadata relevant for a collection or data object is explicitly stored for that specific collection or data object. Some metadata, or relevance of metadata, is also implied by the file system structure.

For example there might be a collection named after a study ID which contains a collection named “experiments”. This implies that the experiments in this “experiments” collection belong to that study. If we then look at an experiment contained in “experiments”, the metadata stored for it are also relevant for the subject that took part in that experiment. But the information that this subject and experiment belong together in the first place is stored in metadata for yet another completely different collection.

In MrDataSearch, that struggle is minimized because everything is connected intuitively in the graph. Once I got an understanding of where specific metadata were stored in MrData I used that knowledge to create a design of the intuitive connections between concepts and their metadata which then became the basis for MrDataSearch’s graph database structure.

Another point that came up in the context of these metadata was their quality. The naming on one hand: An experiment ID can have a different attribute name depending on which collection it is stored into and who stored it there. If it was automatically stored by Castellum, the attribute name and value can be trusted. If a researcher put it in by hand, it could contain anything. Fields filled in by hand would sometimes contain what was expected of them, sometimes the information contained was faulty, and many times a person had put in not only what the attribute name suggested, but also added other parameters in the same field. To deal with this issue, I had to figure out the source each piece of information came from and which information could be trusted and used to automatically build a graph database from.

Not only did the (meta-) data fields sourced from manual input make it difficult to find reliable information for connections in the graph, but it sometimes also caused errors when added to the RDF graph. Those errors were mostly caused by spaces and special characters in file names, metadata attribute names and the attributes themselves. To address that, all spaces in names were caught with regex and replaced by underscores for the RDF graph. All other special characters were caught by the use of `quote` from the Python `urllib` package to convert all names into valid URIs.

Another important discovery during the implementation was the fact that subject IDs are only unique within one study. As the plan was to implement MrDataSearch across studies, this was solved by prepending the relative study ID to every subject ID.

4.4 Conclusion

In this section we will briefly review the problems we wanted to tackle, the implementation and results. We will also discuss to what extent the original problems were solved by the implementation of MrDataSearch.

The main issue we wanted to address with MrDataSearch was the lack of flexible and complete searchability by metadata. Specifically, users needed a solution for metadata searches across metadata on different iRODS collections and data objects that could also draw metadata from the iRODS file system structure.

For searches within a single study, MrDataSearch provides that solution. It uses a graph database, specifically designed with intuitive connections for metadata in the MrData iRODS store, as a data structure that can easily be searched by metadata. All the questions that we addressed in section 1.2, i.e.

- listing all experiments for a specific subject whose scientific metadata fulfill certain criteria
- determining if two experiments belong to the same subject and
- selecting all subjects with certain metadata criteria and returning functional data on them

can be answered within one study by posing the right SPARQL queries to MrDataSearch. MrDataSearch also seems to solve the runtime problem since all tested queries produced their output within a few seconds, most of them even with runtimes under one second.

However, some problems still remain and during the implementation new problems came up, which now need to be addressed in future work.

Searching across subjects in multiple studies is still problematic. Since MrDataSearch only has access to the pseudonymized subject IDs, which are only valid within one study, this could not be achieved yet. To implement this, a cross-reference of subject IDs across studies would have to be extracted from Castellum, since information on which people participated in which studies and experiments is exclusively stored there. This exclusive storage of PII in Castellum and anonymization of subjects across studies is a feature implemented for enhanced privacy, which means a data protection decision would have to be made in order to export this cross-reference.

Another challenge with the current version of MrDataSearch is that data from the graph database can only be searched or filtered with SPARQL queries, which means that users need to be able to write SPARQL queries. This can be a challenge for people not yet familiar with the SPARQL query language.

In future work we will explore different possibilities for addressing these issues to improve the already successful implementation of MrDataSearch.

Chapter 5

Outlook

Although the implementation of MrDataSearch described in this thesis already helps with many searchability problems in MrData, there remain opportunities to extend and improve the system further. In this final chapter we will first look at how this project is usable for similar work and then conclude by discussing planned future work to improve and expand MrDataSearch.

5.1 Usability for similar work

This project shows that using a graph database to store metadata can be an effective way to increase searchability of metadata for research data stored in complex iRODS structures like MrData. Assuming that MrData is not the only iRODS-based system that faces challenges with searchability via metadata, the techniques described in this work could be of use in similar iRODS metadata search cases.

In this case, the archival backing storage used was iRODS. However, it is also worth mentioning that MrDataSearch is not dependent on iRODS and can be modified to also work for other archival systems. In the event that another data and metadata storage system were to be chosen over iRODS, a metadata search infrastructure that stands on its own creates a separation of concerns between data storage and metadata handling.

The code for this project, split down into its functions, is provided and explained in chapter 3, in order to make it as reusable as possible. It shows how to model metadata from iRODS into a graph database to then query them more efficiently.

Similar to the code designed for MrDataSearch one could follow the same steps to design an RDF graph database for other research data and their metadata. In the case of MrDataSearch, the results showed that a graph database with

connections that are intuitive to the user leads to a graph database design that can then also be queried intuitively and can increase searchability.

Since this approach worked out well for MrDataSearch it is reasonable to hypothesize that it may also be effective for addressing similar metadata search challenges.

5.2 Future Work

The current version of MrDataSearch provides a graph database, which can be queried with logical and intuitive SPARQL queries in a reasonable amount of time. Compared to what researchers were able to do before using iRODS tools this is already a big enhancement. However, there is still room for improvement and features we want to add in the future.

We plan to implement an ontology [24] that gives formal definitions for concepts and predicates used in the MrDataSearch graph database. Right now, all people working with MrData have a somewhat uniform collective understanding of what specific terms mean in the context of our project. Currently, these concepts are defined in the MrDataSearch python code as constants used in generating RDF triples. However, it is important to record the definitions for these concepts somewhere, so everyone will be on the same page and new or outside people can understand the concepts easier. A formal ontology will enable this in a computer readable way.

The next issue we want to work on is to make posing queries to the graph database more accessible for researchers. Currently, the only way to search or filter the information in the graph database, is to write SPARQL queries manually, which is a skill that takes time to master.

To solve this, one option could be to design a small web frontend with drop-down menus, where researchers can filter what aspects of metadata they want for their selection, and then get the experiment-/study-ID and/or file names in iRODS for everything that fits their metadata search.

Another option that we want to look into is the usage of a large language model (LLM) for writing SPARQL queries. The idea is that researchers would tell the LLM what data they are looking for in natural language and the LLM would then write the corresponding SPARQL query.

Another topic we want to explore is if we can make it possible to search across subjects in multiple studies. As mentioned in section 4.4, we would need a cross-reference of subject IDs across studies to be able to implement this, and it would also require a new assessment of data protection. This inclusion of

more sensitive data could lead to us having to restrict the queries that can be posed to the graph database, which is another aspect that we are considering when exploring our options on how to make posing queries more accessible.

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List of Abbreviations

- AVU** attribute value unit
- DBMS** database management system
- DICOM** Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
- GDPR** General Data Protection Regulation
- iRODS** Integrated Rule-Oriented Data System
- LLM** large language model
- MPI** Max Planck Institute
- MP RAGE** Magnetization-Prepared Rapid Gradient Echo
- MRI** magnetic resonance imaging
- NIFTI** Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative
- PII** person identifiable information
- RDBMS** relational database management system
- RDF** Resource Description Framework
- SPARQL** SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
- Turtle** Terse RDF Triple Language
- W3C** World Wide Web Consortium

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